

PROPERTIES AND FAILURE PREDICTION OF INTERPLY HYBRID COMPOSITES OF GLASS AND SELF-REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

Farzaneh. Hassani¹, Peter. J. Martin², M. Ali. Aravand¹ and Brian. G. Falzon^{1*}

¹ Advanced Composite Research Group, School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Queen's University Belfast, UK

² Polymer Processing Research Centre, Queen's University Belfast, UK

* Brian G. Falzon (b.falzon@qub.ac.uk)

Keywords: *Self-reinforced composites, glass fibre, polypropylene, hybrid composites*

ABSTRACT

Self-reinforced polypropylene composites (SRPP) exhibit high ductility and failure strain. However, their relatively low stiffness restricts their application. Hybridisation using a higher stiffness/strength composite mitigates this shortcoming and gives rise to a novel lightweight structural material. The current work investigates the interleaving of continuous glass fibre reinforcement with SRPP. Maleic anhydride- modified polypropylene films were used for resin film infusion of the glass-fibres. This modified polymer is highly compatible with glass fibres and prevents premature failure of the layer due to delamination and poor bonding.

Laminates were tested in tension to explore stiffness enhancement, damage initiation, and failure strain/strength. It is shown that with appropriate hybridisation, the sharp load drop, which occurs at the lower failure strain of the glass/PP plies, can be prevented. Various lay-ups were considered and it was shown that a SRPP/Glass ratio of 10 to 2 is the critical ratio below which the hybrid system exhibits load drop and diverges from pseudo-ductility. An analytical approach has also been used in order to predict the hybrid behavior of the laminates, based on a previously developed model for carbon/glass thin-ply hybrid systems. The failure criteria, corresponding to the sudden failure of the hybrid laminate are calculated analytically, where the results are compared with experimental measurements.

1. INTRODUCTION

Self-reinforced composites (SRC) are materials with a similar polymer for the matrix and the reinforcement. The all-thermoplastic structure ensures advantages such as a strong fibre/matrix interface, recyclability and ductility with high energy absorbance capability compared to conventional composites. High stiffness/low strain composites may be hybridised with self-reinforce materials to increase the ductility of the former. In this work hybridisation of glass fibre/polypropylene with self-reinforced polypropylene (SRPP) composite is aimed to introduce a novel and lightweight material with gradual progressive failure (mitigating the possibility of catastrophic failure) and high ductility. Glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (GRPP) composites are widely used in the automotive industry. However, they are limited ductility and fail at relatively low strains. Incorporating a self-reinforced polypropylene composite into the structure can enhance these properties by introducing pseudo-ductility in the laminate. Two main criteria need to be satisfied to reach pseudo-ductility and exhibit progressive failure [1]. Firstly, the low strain material (GRPP) must not suddenly debond from the high strain layer (SRPP) during loading. This can be fulfilled once the fracture toughness at the failure strain of the glass/PP is lower than the mode II fracture toughness at the interface of the SRPP and GRPP. Secondly, the volume fraction and strength of the SRPP must be such as to assure that the load can withstand beyond the initial failure of GRPP. There are also other factors which can affect the hybrid behaviour, including matrix/fibre interfacial strength, stacking sequence and the fibre volume fraction [2- 5]. Volume fraction of each constituent as well as the thickness of the laminae is also important in predicting of the hybrid

elastic properties and the failure behaviour [4]. Criteria for the minimum and maximum thicknesses for the low strain constituent, in a hybrid, to achieve a pseudo-ductile material were proposed by Czel [5].

The current work investigates the tensile behaviour of interleaved hybrid laminated hybrids of SRPP composites with GRPP. The tensile modulus and failure behaviour are determined and the results compared with predicted values using the analytical models.

2. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

2.1. Materials and Processing

Interleaved hybrid laminates of GRPP and SRPP were manufactured using a hot compaction process. Each layer of Textreme® glass fabric, details of which are presented in Table 1, was placed between two layers of modified polypropylene films of 60 µm thickness to create a GRPP lamina. Polypropylene films were manufactured by dry mixing PP granules with 3wt% of Fusabond P353 (Maleic-Anhydride polypropylene masterbatch) and melt mixing in a single screw extruder equipped with a slit die to produce the maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (PP-MA) film with the required thickness. Polypropylene granules used for GRPP composite were the same grade as the matrix in the self-reinforced polypropylene provided by Don and Low Ltd. Self-reinforced polypropylene tapes have a core/shell structure consisting of a matrix of a lower melting point than the core and a highly oriented core which acts as the reinforcement. The tapes having a width of 2 mm and thickness of 55-60 µm are weaved to form the SRPP fabric. The SRPP fabric reinforcement used in this work was in the form of a plain weave with an areal density of 130g/m² and a core/shell weight ratio of 0.85-0.9. The manufactured layups had 10 layers of SRPP fabrics with 1-4 layers of GRPP composite in a block assembly in which the GRPP laminae were placed in the middle of the SRPP fabrics. The hybrid layup was then consolidated in a Platen Press capable of applying 100 bar pressure over an area of 200 by 200 mm. All panels were manufactured at the compaction temperature of 145° C under 70 bar pressure for 5 minutes. The processing parameters were decided based on the approach reported earlier for the same self-reinforced polypropylene [6]. Figure 1 shows the cross-section of a consolidated laminate. As shown, full impregnation of the matrix has been achieved in the consolidation process.

Table 1- Properties of Glass fabric

Property	Unit	Value
Areal Density	g/m ²	80
Surface treatment	-	Silane
Fibre architecture	-	Plain Weave Warp: EC9, 13 tex Weft: EC9, 13 tex

Figure 1- Optical micrograph of the cross-section of a interleaved hybrid composites of 10 layers of SRPP and 4 layers of GRPP, 5SR/4GRPP/5SR.

2.2. Volume Fraction Analysis

The matrix burn-off technique was employed to measure the volume fraction of the glass fibres in the hybrid laminates based on the Standard ASTM D2584 [7] five grams of each hybrid panel was weighed and heated in a furnace at 565°C until all the polypropylene was burnt. The panels were weighed every 3 hrs until the difference between the successive measurements is less than 5%. To calculate the glass fibre volume fraction all the polypropylene in the system is considered to have the same density. The weight percentage of the remaining material was using Equation 1 and the overall glass fibre volume fraction in the hybrid laminate was calculated using Equation 2 with 0.91 and 1.9 gr/cm³ as the densities of the polypropylene and glass fabric, respectively.

$$W_f = [1 - (\frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1})] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$W_f = \frac{\frac{\rho_f}{\rho_m}}{\frac{\rho_f}{\rho_m} V_f + V_m} V_f \quad (2)$$

$W_{1,2,f}$: Weight of specimen, residue and the residue weight fraction

$\rho_{f,m}$: Density of the fibre and the matrix

$V_{f,m}$: Volume fraction of the fibre and matrix

2.3. Tensile Test

The standard ASTM D3039 was used to measure the tensile properties of the hybrid laminates [8]. Specimens with dimensions of 20 x 200 mm were cut from the consolidated laminates and tested at a strain rate of 4%/min (corresponding to a crosshead displacement rate of 5mm/min) in a Zwick 100 tensile machine with a load cell 100 kN. A 2D digital image correlation was used to measure the strains. At least 5 specimens were tested for each lay-up.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Tensile test results and failure prediction

The thicknesses and volume fractions of the hybrid laminates are summarised in Table 2. Block assemblies with GRPP layers sandwich between 5 layers of SRPP on top and 5 layers on bottom were investigated in order to apply the previously developed analytical relations for the block sandwich hybrids [9].

Table 2- Specifications of the hybrid specimens tested in tension.

Hybrid	Nominal Thickness (mm)	GRPP volume fraction (%)	Glass fibre volume fraction (%)
5SR/1GRPP/5SR	1.4	9.6	3.6
5SR/2GRPP/5SR	1.57	16	6.0
5SR/3GRPP/5SR	1.63	21	7.9
5SR/4GRPP/5SR	1.75	25.8	9.7

Table 3 shows that the tensile moduli of the hybrid laminates increase by adding the GRPP composites. The experimental results are also compared with the elastic moduli predicted based on the rule of mixtures (RoM). The rule of mixtures shows good agreement with those of the experimental results. The number beside each column shows the increase compared to the stiffness of SRPP.

Table 3- Tensile modulus of hybrid laminates from experiment and calculations from the rule of mixtures (RoM).

Hybrid layup	Tensile Modulus Experiment (GPa)	Tensile Modulus Rule of Mixtures (GPa)	Tensile Modulus increase compared to SRPP (%)
SRPP	3.72	-	-
5SR/1GRPP/5SR	4.42	4.77	28
5SR/2GRPP/5SR	4.89	4.90	31
5SR/3GRPP/5SR	5.25	5.26	41
5SR/4GRPP/5SR	5.41	5.6	45

Typical stress-strain curves of the hybrid laminates are presented in Figure 2. Pseudo-ductility was achieved for one and two layers of GRPP (1GRPP and 2GRPP) with an overall glass fibre volume fraction of 16% or less. Therefore, the critical thickness of GRPP layer to achieve pseudo-ductility is assumed to be 0.32 mm (the thickness of two GRPP lamina). Czel [1] has shown that having a critical thickness of the low strain failure material in a hybrid composite, mode II fracture toughness can be approximated from the strain energy release rate (G) for the pull-out of the interleaved low strain failure layer (GRPP):

$$G = \frac{\sigma^2 h^2}{4(E_1 t_1 + E_2 t_2)} - \frac{\sigma^2 h^2}{4E_1 t_1} \quad (3)$$

$t_{1,2}$: Thickness of SRPP and GRPP (mm)

$E_{1,2}$: Tensile moduli of SRPP and GRPP (MPa)

G : Strain energy release rate kJ/m^2

Substituting the above-mentioned values, mode II fracture toughness is approximated to be 0.430 kJ/m^2 . Taking this value for the mode II fracture toughness of delamination at the interface of the SRPP and GRPP, the stress at which delamination occurs, σ_d , can be calculated for each layup. Furthermore, assuming that SRPP behaves elastically before the failure of the low failure strain layer (GRPP), the overall stress (σ_f) at which the glass/PP layer fails can be calculated from:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{E_1 \varepsilon_{(gf)} t_1 + \sigma_2 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} \quad (4)$$

The stress applied to the GRPP layer at the failure strain can be substituted with the strength of the material, $\sigma_2 = S_{GRPP} = 147 \text{ MPa}$. After the GRPP layer has failed and lost its load carrying capacity, the applied load to the specimen is carried by SRPP [10]. Therefore, the stress at which the specimen fails is predicted as:

$$\sigma_{f, \text{overall}} = \frac{S_{SRPP} t_1}{t_1 + t_2} \quad (5)$$

S_{SRPP} : Strength of the SRPP

Error! Reference source not found. demonstrates the experimental stress-strain curves of the hybrid specimens tested in tension and Table 4 summarises the experimental results together with the analytical calculations. As shown, the analytical model predicts the initial modulus, pseudo-ductility and final failure of the laminate with good accuracy. However, it is worth mentioning that the failure strain of the GRPP layer is higher when it is interleaved between the SRPP layers compared to when it is tested in a pure form. This is a common reported finding in hybrid research and has been demonstrated by Hayashi [10-11] for unidirectional glass/carbon epoxy hybrid composites and also in the later work of Czel et al [9]. However, this is not applied in the current failure prediction. therefore, the current model has only investigated the critical stresses for failure prediction and further work needs to be completed to extend the predictions for the pseudo-ductile and the failure strains of the interply hybrid structure.

Figure 2- Representative stress-strain curve of the hybrid laminates with 10 layers of SRPP and different layers of GRPP.

Table 4-Failure behaviour prediction for the interleaved hybrid laminates tested in tension.

Hybrid configuration	Experimental			Analytical			
	σ_f (MPa)	σ_d (MPa)	$\sigma_{f,overall}$ (MPa)	σ_f (MPa)	σ_d (MPa)	$\sigma_{f,overall}$ (MPa)	Criteria
5SR/1GRPP/5SR	78.9±0.72	82.8±2.37	208.6±5.01	81.9	120.8	192.4	$\sigma_d > \sigma_f$ Pseudo-ductile
5SR/2GRPP/5SR	83.2±1.27	81.8±1.64	182.9±5.37	87.8	86.68	171.6	$\sigma_d \cong \sigma_f$ Pseudo-ductile
5SR/3GRPP/5SR	100.5±1.48	91.6±1.35	176.9±4.01	92.8	70.98	165.3	$\sigma_d < \sigma_f$ Load drop
5SR/4GRPP/5SR	100.1±2.87	90.7±2.77	163.5±5.4	97.1	61.2	153.9	$\sigma_d < \sigma_f$ Load drop

4. CONCLUSIONS

As a result of this work it was concluded that:

- 28-45% increase in stiffness was achieved by adding 1 to 4 layers of GRPP.
- The critical thickness for pseudo-ductility was 0.28 mm.
- The equation for the strain energy release rate was adopted to successfully predict the criteria to show pseudo-ductility.

- The analytical model successfully predicted the pseudo-ductility, stress drop in the stress-strain curve and the failure stresses for the hybrid laminates

5. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Czél and M. R. Wisnom, “Demonstration of pseudo-ductility in high performance glass/epoxy composites by hybridisation with thin-ply carbon prepreg,” *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 52, pp. 23–30, 2013.
- [2] I. D. G. Ary Subagia, Y. Kim, L. D. Tijjng, C. S. Kim, and H. K. Shon, “Effect of stacking sequence on the flexural properties of hybrid composites reinforced with carbon and basalt fibers,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 58, pp. 251–258, 2014.
- [3] Y. Swolfs, Y. Meerten, P. Hine, I. Ward, I. Verpoest, and L. Gorbatikh, “Introducing ductility in hybrid carbon fibre/self-reinforced composites through control of the damage mechanisms,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 131, pp. 259–265, 2015.
- [4] G. Czél, M. Jalalvand, M. R. Wisnom, and T. Czigány, “Design and characterisation of high performance, pseudo-ductile all-carbon/epoxy unidirectional hybrid composites,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 111, pp. 348–356, 2017.
- [5] G. Czél, M. Jalalvand, and M. R. Wisnom, “Design and characterisation of advanced pseudo-ductile unidirectional thin-ply carbon/epoxy-glass/epoxy hybrid composites,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 143, pp. 362–370, 2016.
- [6] F. Hassani, P. J. Martin, B. G. Falzon “The Effect of Processing on the Mechanical Properties of Self-Reinforced Composites,” in *21st International ESAFORM Conference on Material Forming*, 2018.
- [7] “ASTM D2584-18, Standard Test Method for Ignition Loss of Cured Reinforced Resins, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2018, www.astm.org.”
- [8] “ASTM_D3039, Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials.” ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2017.
- [9] G. Czél, M. Jalalvand, and M. R. Wisnom, “Demonstration of pseudo-ductility in unidirectional hybrid composites made of discontinuous carbon/epoxy and continuous glass/epoxy plies,” *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 72, pp. 75–84, 2015.
- [10] M. Selezneva *et al.*, “Predicting Tensile Behaviour of Hybrid Carbon Fibre / Srp Composites : How Far Can Analytical Models Take Us ?,” no. June, pp. 24–28, 2018.
- [11] H. T., “Development of new material properties by hybrid composition. 1st report,” *Compos. Mater.*, vol. 1, pp. 18–20, 1972.
- [12] K. M. Hayashi T, Koyama K, Yamazaki A, “Development of new material properties by hybrid composition. 2nd report,” *Compoaiste Mater.*, vol. 1, pp. 21–25, 1972.